

GENETICS AND BIOTECHNOLOGY

ANIMAL HUSBANDRY AS A FLOW OF ENERGY IN THE FUNCTIONING OF AGRICULTURAL SYSTEMS (development forecast)

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Abstract

The increase in the population of the Earth, the impact of adverse environmental factors on agricultural production requires the transfer of animal husbandry from concentrated types of diets to year-round grass fodder, the assessment of genetic resources, and changes in the strategy of animal breeding. In the short term, animal husbandry is proposed to be considered as: 1) a source of formation of food products and raw materials; 2) energy flows in the functioning of agricultural systems.

Keywords: food problems, animal breeds and species, energy, balanced agrarian formations.

Introduction. In all countries of the world, the modern development of animal husbandry is based on the maximum distribution of specialized high-intensity and productive breeds of animals that require special production technologies with significant energy costs and scientific achievements, especially the selection and genetic profile and veterinary safety.

In most developed countries, the livestock development strategy was based on the use of animals with the maximum possible productivity: In dairy cattle breeding, the milk yield level is typically between 7,000 to 10,000 kg per lactation with a somatic cell count of 200,000 cells per milliliter of milk. In beef cattle breeding, the average daily gain in live weight should be at least 1.5-2 kg. In egg poultry farming, the expected yield is between 300-360 eggs per laying hen. The energy feed requirement of the animals was provided by feeding rations saturated with grain high-protein ingredients, vitamins, micro- and macroelements [3].

Will these factors remain the main ones in the near future?

Source Analysis. The efficiency of agricultural production is heavily influenced by a number of key factors. Prior to 1800, the world utilized 7.4 billion hectares of land. By 1960, with a population of 3 billion people, only 1.5 billion hectares of land remained. By the year 2000, there was only 0.27 hectares of arable land available per person. With the degradation of 12 million hectares of land every year, it is estimated that in 30-40 years there will only be enough food to feed 2 billion people [7].

According to the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the issue of food scarcity is often hidden behind financial crises. In 2006, food prices increased by 12%, and by 2008 they had risen by 50%. The FAO also reports that food consumption per capita is rising in countries such as China and India. Shockingly, as of 2010, the number of starving people worldwide is approaching 1 billion [6, 12].

Results of research and discussion. The model of the livestock industry in the near future must be built on a systemic basis, taking into account many factors that are interconnected in terms of their impact or end

result. For example, many assess the livestock industry based on consumer psychology, forgetting that animals have existed in nature even before the formation of human communities, i.e. they are part of the bioecosystem [10].

Without a developed "livestock" sector, the planetary ecosystem can cause consequences that are difficult to compensate for. Residents of the Carpathian, Forest-Steppe, and Polissya regions of Ukraine have noted the following facts: a decrease in the number of large cattle, sheep, goats, and horses has led to an increase in forest fires and the overgrowth of land suitable for agricultural production with shrubs. Animals excrete 50% or more of the volume of food they consume, which subsequently forms an irreplaceable organic fertilizer - manure - that provides a lumpy soil structure. This allows air and water to penetrate to the roots of plants.

Despite a number of international agreements, the environmental situation in most developed countries continues to deteriorate, which raises concerns about access to nutritious food, especially for children. An increasing number of scientific publications suggest that animals with a multi-chambered stomach provide "clean" or "pure" foods even from polluted areas of land.

The energy component in the life of the human community will become more complex and more expensive, so technological solutions for keeping and feeding animals should take this perspective into account. It is necessary to gradually, while circumstances still allow, to return the livestock industry to its natural environment: practice grazing cows, place animals in lightweight structures, create windbreaks in walking areas, etc. Therefore, grassland farming, natural and created by man on the basis of fast-growing grasses and resistant to trampling and temporary flooding, is becoming an urgent problem in the near future, taking into account selection in crop production and animal husbandry.

Scientists believe that most of the grain feed - corn, wheat, rye, triticale, barley and others will be fed to poultry and pigs, so dairy cattle, as the basis of ani-

mal husbandry in most countries of the world, will receive less nutritious diets that will not be able to provide long-term stable daily milk yields at the level of 30-40 kg of milk and more. These circumstances call into question the purposeful selection of specialized dairy breeds only for a maximum productivity of 10 thousand kg of milk and more.

Countries such as New Zealand, Australia and others have become world leaders in milk production, using climatic factors and breeds that efficiently use pastures and ensiled forage.

Consequently, in the near future, grain and concentrated protein feed for animals will have to be replaced by vegetable feed - grass, hay, haylage, silage.

Naturally, in this situation, the priorities of animal breeds and species will change. Combined (milk-meat) and specialized meat breeds, which produce products mainly through the processing of vegetable raw materials, will claim the first place. It is known that cows that make good use of natural meadows and pastures graze an average of 8 hours a day and the grass consumed is enough to produce 20 kg of milk, i.e. their productivity per lactation will be 4 - 4.5 thousand kg of milk with a fat content of 4.0 - 4.2% and a protein content of 3.7 - 3.9%. Breeders especially appreciate the stability of lactation (stability of the lactation curve). With a live weight of 600-650 kg, these physiological loads on the body of cows do not cause metabolic disorders, especially fertility and the duration of economic use of cows. Ultimately, such animals produce 4 calves and 16-20 tons of high quality milk in 4-5 lactations, consuming haylage, silage of high energy value. Approximately the same gross lifetime milk yield is given by Holstein cows for 2-2.5 lactations, however, veterinary costs for them amount to up to 10% of the value of the gross product. It is also known that Holstein milk contains proteins of the AA and AB genotypes, which do not ensure the production of high-quality hard cheeses of the "Swiss" type, which is why the United States is forced to import these cheeses [1].

The value of combined breeds of dairy cattle is also in the fact that they produce high quality beef with minimal consumption of concentrated feed and maximum use of plant waste from the processing industry. In this aspect, Simmental, Swiss, Montbéliarde, Salers and other cattle continue to lead.

Bringing animals closer to the conditions of their natural environment, we inevitably face the problem of using native domestic breeds (red steppe, Simmental, white-headed Ukrainian, brown Carpathian, gray Ukrainian, etc.). The most important advantage of native breeds is good health, resistance to specific viral infections, duration of economic use (obtaining 5 or more calves from cows), high quality of milk and meat, and the ability to survive in arid zones.

Gradually, in zootechnics, the position is being established that the main features of the selection of animals are fertility and the duration of economic use. It is they that should, first of all, be taken into account when assessing the gene pool and genetic resources [4].

In dairy cattle breeding, the most time-consuming technological process is milking cows, therefore, along with the requirement of stable average daily milk yields

at the level of 15-20 kg of milk during lactation, their suitability for machine milking is necessary.

It is also necessary to carefully comprehensively study the problem of using sexed sperm (Sexed Semen) of sires to obtain female offspring (heifers) in the offspring of cows. The use of sexed sperm would be biologically justified if the presence of the Y chromosome were the only factor in the formation of female organisms.

Geneticists have challenged the commonly accepted theory of the universal sexual status of newborn offspring. As a result, alternative theories have been formulated, including the existence of four types of chromosome sex determination in animals and the balance theory of sex determination. This theory suggests that initial sex determination using heterochromosomes depends not only on the ratio of the strength of genes located in sex heterochromosomes and autosomes but also on other factors. The phenomenon of parthenogenesis, as observed in rabbits, also highlights the complexity of the sex determination process and indicates that it cannot be reduced solely to the action of X or Y chromosomes. In most European countries, the widespread use of sexed sperm is not recommended. However, it is recognized that the use of sexed sperm once may be expedient for the purpose of rapidly increasing the number of breeding stock, with a transition to the traditional system of herd reproduction technology in the future.

Recognizing the need to develop modern technological solutions for new farms with large animal populations that produce high yields of finished products at industrial volumes and using bioenergy sources is crucial for addressing complex challenges at all levels of society.

Therefore, the selection strategy in dairy cattle breeding needs to be reviewed.

To reduce energy costs, modern animal farming technologies aim to "return" animals to their natural habitats. This underscores the importance of genetic resources from genera such as buffalo, lobed banteng bulls, gaurs, gayals, yaks, and bison, which become important for sustainable breeding practices.

Domestic buffaloes on a balanced diet can reach a live weight of 600-800 kg and produce up to 2000 kg of milk with a fat content of 9.0% and a protein content of 6.0%. This is equivalent to about 4000 kg of standardized cow's milk. Considering that domestic buffaloes can live up to 40-50 years and their females can produce 15-20 calves in their lifetime, as well as their natural resistance to diseases and ability to consume and process a large amount of roughage, including reeds found in lakes and seas, the value of this animal species is undeniable.

The Association of German Breeders is helping Transcarpathian farmers to conserve Ukrainian buffaloes. In Ukraine, near Kiev, a unique herd of buffaloes has been created, and genetic examinations have been conducted using short-chain satellite DNA. In addition, scientific studies have been conducted on their milk and meat productivity, including their amino acid composition [5].

The cost of fossil energy sources is constantly increasing, leading world analysts to note another feature of 21st century agricultural production: crop and livestock production should not only provide food products but also produce bioenergy (biodiesel, biogas, alcohol). Scientific research has shown that it is possible to balance the production of biofuels and food raw materials by creating waste-free production cycles and integrating modern technological solutions such as biogas, biofuel, biohumus, and others, which strengthen a country's energy independence and food security [2].

Scientific calculations show that with a cattle population density of ≈ 1 conditional head per 1 ha of arable land, it is possible to produce 400 kg/ha of food, 200 l/ha of biodiesel with waste disposal to methane and biolumus for subsequent transition to organic agricultural production [8].

Only in this case, agricultural production will be less dependent on artificially high energy prices. There remains, apparently, an eternally fair statement that the finished product of an agricultural enterprise always gives more income than the original raw material. There is an obvious need for a fundamental transfer of agricultural production to bioenergy and a waste-free process of technological cycles, which involves the use of science-based technological solutions to systemic problems.

To overcome the impending "world hunger", humanity will have to formulate a methodology for the use of bioresources of the aquatic environment from other positions, incl. and the creation of underwater settlements and underwater farms. The development of the aquatic environment of oceans, seas, rivers, etc., and their biological resources is carried out in many countries of the world, especially in Japan, the USA, Norway, and Sweden. Figuratively speaking, research is being carried out in two main directions: 1 - on the biology of the reproduction of "wild fauna" (fish, seals, whales and other classes of animals), in order to prevent predatory capture of the biomass of the aquatic environment, and 2 - to promote an increase in the production of the oceans, the creation of underwater farms of marine animal husbandry under human control at a depth of up to 20 m. The amount of protein obtained from animal origin and its quality per unit of water surface is many times greater than the effectiveness of land-based animal husbandry.

Scientific research projects and the life practice of the natives of Oceania, the Caribbean and the Pacific indicate the need to develop international agreements regarding the sustainable management and conservation of the water resources of the planet Earth. The problem of the ratio of animal species in stable ecosystems and agroecosystems deserves attention. Often, the fauna of biosphere reserves is taken as a basis for comparison. However, the system for recording the number of animals and their seasonal migration is still far from perfect. An important aspect is which species of farm animals should be given preferences for reproduction in different ecological and climatic conditions. For example, some experts, considering the possible consequences of climate change on Earth, believe that goats

and sheep will become the real breadwinners of humanity. Goats have been bred on the Korean Peninsula for over 700 years, and their meat is not just used but also considered a healthy medicinal product. Feral Boer and Australian goats are used [6].

In India, the Murrah breed of buffaloes is predominantly bred. 33 breeding farms have been established, including those with the Surti breed. Almost 200,000 llamas are successfully used in Argentina. Scientific support is provided by the National Institute of Agricultural Technology (Instituto Nacional de Tecnología Agropecuaria).

The world's largest commercial population of beef cattle is registered in Brazil. However, the rapid transformation of the livestock industry is possible only in pig and poultry farming, due to their high reproductive capacity. In this aspect, industrial rabbit breeding is also of interest.

In terms of the number of local breeds, birds occupy first place with 360, hybrids with 530 crosses. In second place in the world in terms of the number of local breeds are goats with 419 and sheep with 220. These genetic resources will determine the strategy for the development of animal husbandry in various regions of the globe in the near future.

Research on nanotechnologies in plant and animal husbandry deserves attention, i.e. technologies for manipulating substances at the atomic and molecular levels, which ensure their interaction, as well as quantum effects on the structures of the body, including those that affect stress resistance and metabolic processes [9]. Nanotechnologies have already been tested in veterinary medicine. Nanochelates of metals have been used for disinfecting food products of plant origin, sanitizing udder teats to prevent and treat mastitis in cows, silver nanoparticles, etc. Nanostructural aspects of veterinary homeopathy are intensively discussed in the literature.

In scientific grants from the USA, Great Britain, Germany, more and more funds are directed to research on bioreactors for producing liver cells, stem cells, hormones, muscle tissue, etc. Therefore, the genetic resources of farm animals should be under the control and protection of the state. The future of animal husbandry depends on the level of knowledge of the animal genotype and the norm of the genotype-environment interaction.

The noted trends in the development of livestock industries indicate that a purely consumer attitude of a person to animal husbandry will gradually be replaced by the integrated use of genetically determined resources of the animal world in providing humanity on the planet Earth in food, the energy of biosystems and complementary flows of substances and energy in the planetary ecosystem. In practice, in modern conditions, a person works with animal ecotypes, realizing the need for a systematic analysis and prediction of the most likely consequences of disturbances even in small parts of a functioning system in which the Sun and plants are the determining factors in the development of systems of subsequent levels.

Conclusion

1. An increase in the population of the Earth, the impact of adverse environmental factors on agricultural production reduce the energy and feed base of concentrated feed in the diet of animals, which necessitates the transfer of the livestock industry to grass and silage feed (year-round), a change in the breeding strategy, and the assessment of animal genetic resources.

2. It is quite obvious that it is expedient to return to the breeding of native breeds of Ukraine: red steppe, Simmental, Lebedinskaya, gray Ukrainian, white-headed Ukrainian, brown Carpathian and others, improved according to the technological requirements of industrial technology and having high fertility, which will ensure expanded reproduction of the livestock of these breeds, which very problematic to achieve when using "high-blooded" Holstein crosses due to their poor reproductive ability.

3. Those populations that are most amenable to genetic transformation are those that have a high reproduction rate and viability.

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